

ALOE FLOWER AND ITS MEDICINAL PROPERTIES

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Abstract. *This plant, originally from Africa, came to our country several centuries ago. Now in our country there are several types of aloe. It is grown at home as an ornamental and medicinal plant. About 180 species of this plant are known. Canned aloe leaf juice is used to treat various wounds, burns, gastritis and colitis. Aloe is a group of evergreen perennial herbs (sometimes trees) belonging to the tulip family. their leaves are thick, rough, thick and prickly. Canned juice from aloe leaves is used to treat various wounds, burns, gastritis. Aloe leaf extract, rich in biostimulants, is preserved and injected under the skin as a means of increasing the body's strength.*

Keywords: *Aloe, immunostimulant, conjunctivitis, stimulant.*

INTRODUCTION

In folk medicine, aloe leaf and its juice are used to treat various diseases: stomach and duodenal ulcers, pulmonary tuberculosis, etc. Aloe contains a substance that prevents the growth of bacteria. That is why, when a bee stings or when the skin is cut with a knife or other object, the aloe leaf is cut along the middle and tied up to prevent it from festering. It also neutralizes bee venom. For medical purposes, the juice is extracted from a freshly picked aloe leaf and preserved with alcohol. The juice has bactericidal properties and is used in the treatment of burns, infectious and other wounds, some diseases of the stomach and intestines (colitis, gastritis, etc.). Aqueous aloe extract has immunostimulating properties and protects the body from various diseases. Aloe emulsion is also prepared by adding sesame oil and eucalyptus essential oil from aloe leaves, which are rich in biogenic stimulants. These drugs increase the

body's ability to fight disease. Therefore, the stimulating liquid extract from aloe leaves is widely used in the treatment of eye diseases (conjunctivitis, vitreous opacity, etc.), chronic arthritis, gastric ulcer and duodenal ulcer [1].

MAIN PART

Aloe emulsion is used to treat skin diseases (dry and weeping epidermatitis) and burns of the 2nd and 3rd degree through ionotherapy. Gynecological diseases are also usually treated with aloe leaf juice against uterine erosion. This is not only a medicinal plant, but also a means of improving appetite. Aloe liquid extract is a preservative for biogenic stimulants derived from plants. The drug stimulates metabolism, improves cellular metabolism, trophism and tissue regeneration, is prescribed to increase the nonspecific resistance of the body [2]. The leaves of the plant contain the following substances: vitamins, including C, E, A and B vitamins: B1, B6, B12, essential oils, amino acids, polysaccharides, mineral salts, organic acids, flavonoids, glycoproteins, folic acid, carotenes and K, There are elements such as Ca, Mg, Zn, Cu. The immunostimulating effect of aloe is due to the presence of polysaccharides and glycoproteins in its composition. Neutral aloe polysaccharides have antimicrobial activity against certain microorganisms. Aloe glycoproteins are involved in the metabolism of bradykinin, help cell proliferation.

Antioxidants are important for health. Aloe vera gel contains Trusted Source powerful antioxidants belonging to a large family of substances known as polyphenols.

These polyphenols, along with several other compounds in aloe vera, help inhibit the growth of certain bacteria that can cause infections in humans [3].

Aloe vera is known for Trusted Source its antibacterial, antiviral, and antiseptic properties. This is part of why it may help heal wounds and treat skin problems.

People most often use aloe vera as a topical medication, rubbing it onto the skin rather than consuming it. In fact, it has a long history of use in treating sores, and particularly burns, including sunburn.

The United States Pharmacopeia describe aloe vera preparations as a skin protectant as early as 1810–1820 [4].

Studies suggest that it is an effective topical treatment for first and second degree burns.

For example, a review Trusted Source of experimental studies found that aloe vera could reduce the healing time of burns by around 9 days compared with conventional medication. It also helped prevent redness, itching, and infections.

The evidence for aloe vera helping heal other types of wound is inconclusive, but the research is promising.

The aloe vera plant has many medicinal properties and the plant must be at least 3 years old to be used as a remedy. The older Aloe: problems and solutions, the higher its healing properties. Due to its bactericidal properties, aloe juice is used for streptococcal and staphylococcal infections. The ability of the plant to accelerate tissue regeneration is used in the treatment of purulent and infected wounds, various injuries, inflammatory diseases and radiation. Substances contained in aloe juice are active against diphtheria and dysentery bacilli. Scientists have extracted from aloe juice an antibiotic used in the treatment of skin diseases and tuberculosis.

CONCLUSION

Ophthalmologists use aloe juice drops to prevent conjunctivitis, myopia, vitreous opacities and cataracts. Aloe juice, used in small doses, facilitates the process of digestion, improves bile secretion, normalizes intestinal motility and has a general strengthening effect on the human body. In gynecological diseases, aloe leaves and juice are usually used as a remedy for uterine erosion and various gynecological inflammatory diseases. Aloe is not only a medicinal plant, but also a remedy that improves appetite. Plant extracts are also useful for headaches and tuberculosis. From the juice squeezed from aloe leaves, gels and creams are prepared for the skin of the face, hands and body.

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